

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION AND NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF FIBER ORIENTATION DURING COMPRESSION MOLDING OF GMT

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ABSTRACT

To predict the fiber orientation in compression molded GMT a 3-dimensional model was developed. Orientation behavior was studied in flat rectangular and circular GMT parts molded in a tool allowing variable cavity geometry. With the aid of black tracers in an otherwise transparent charge the deformation profile could be observed. A simple but extremely fast image processing algorithm was used to determine the orientation state, after having been verified with images of known orientation. The orientation model assumes a mesh type deformation and is based on Dinh and Armstrong. Arbitrary initial orientation and fiber interaction have been accounted for.

INTRODUCTION

Prediction of the fiber orientation during injection or compression molding is of considerable interest because the resulting anisotropy affects a number of elasto- and thermomechanical properties of the part and is partly responsible for warpage and residual stress. In the case of short fiber reinforced plastics or SMC a number of authors have reported successful simulation using the Folgar-Tucker orientation model [1, 2]. This expresses the motion of a fiber as a function of velocity gradients, the orientation distribution and a phenomenological coefficient, which accounts for the fiber's interaction [3]. However, little effort has been made to apply such a model to the particular characteristics of GMT.

While a number of fiber reinforced thermoplasts can be compression molded, the material most frequently employed in industrie is a mat-type GMT, where prior to the impregnation with polypropylene the glass fibers are mechanically bonded in a needle-punch to give a handleable fiber mat. A semi-finished GMT-blank consists of two of these mats. A typical multi-layer charge is characterized by strong bonds within one mat and hardly any linkage between mats.

One of the difficulties when studying the orientation behavior of GMT has been the lack of efficient tools to determine the orientation in a part. Conventional image analysis of polished sections is time consuming and limited to very small samples. Since the fibers in the mat are arranged in a macroscopic manner, only the average value of a large number of such measurements will give the correct result.

IMAGE PROCESSING TO DETERMINE FIBER ORIENTATION

A simple but extremely fast method has been developed that determines the orientation of a fiber mat from greyscale gradients at each pixel of a digitized image. Thus it is not necessary to identify fibers in the image. After the greyscale gradients have been calculated with the *Sobel* operator [4], Eqn. (1) will provide the orientation angle:

$$\theta = (\Delta G_y / \Delta G_x) + \pi/2 \tag{1}$$

The mean greyscale gradient is used for weighing the pixel results, while a local averaging procedure will help to recognize orientation angle close to 0° or 90° and to eliminate noise (s. Fig. 1). For verification a number of test images, drawn by a graphic software to a given orientation distribution, have been analyzed (s. Fig. 2). Even at very high fiber numbers the given and the measured orientation correspond extremely well. Comparison of experimentally determined E-moduli with values obtained from a micromechanical model and the measured orientation distribution also showed fair agreement.

Figure 1. Resolution enhancement through local averaging

Figure 2. Analysis of test images with known orientation distribution

Figure 3. Test stand for orientation measuring

Provided the mat is sufficiently thin, the image can be obtained from a backlit fiber mat, directly filmed with a video camera. Digitalization and subsequent orientation analysis is carried out in 20 seconds with no additional manipulation (s. Fig. 3). The effect of part thickness, aperture, focus and side light has been studied, so that a window was established, within which the results are reliable. In the case of poor contrast or substantial inhomogeneity in the image the program will submit a warning. Currently the use of X-rays is investigated, so that non-destructive evaluation of black GMT parts can be performed.

MOLDING EXPERIMENTS

In a tool with variable mold geometry flat rectangular parts (1-dimensional flow) and circular parts (radial flow) were molded. The press was stopped at various cavity thicknesses, so that the orientation could be measured at different degrees of deformation. In addition molding speed and the number of charges were varied.

Prior to heating small black cylindrical tracers were inserted into the transparent GMT-blanks. After molding, the tracers are smeared across the part and the deformation is easily recognized in a polished cross-section (s. Fig. 4). The tracer experiments have clearly demonstrated the existence of three distinct layers :

- (1) a thin layer of frozen material near the wall, hardly oriented at all,
- (2) a layer with substantial shear deformation and high orientation in the flow direction,
- (3) a center layer with some extensional deformation and orientation which can, however, only be observed in the rectangular part .

In addition, samples of the parts were incinerated in an oven at 600 °C. The remaining fibers are arranged in mats, even after molding. They can easily be separated and weighed to give a fiber distribution in the part. For multi-charge moldings the fibers appeared evenly distributed when the entire stack of mats was weighed. However, the separation into individual mats revealed, that the outer mats have remained in their original position whereas the inner mats have been squeezed out into the flow region (s. Fig. 5). It can be concluded that the GMT charge does not fill the mold with a stretching deformation as in the case of SMC, but rather through a combination of transverse shearing, planar extension and slipping of fiber mats, depending on the number of charges and to what extent the material has solidified near the wall.

Figure 4. Deformation profile in single charge molding

Figure 5. Fiber distribution in multi-charge molding

Figure 6. Part geometry and position of specimen

For orientation measurements a number of samples were taken from the molded part, and incinerated, so that the fiber mat can be analyzed alone (s. Fig. 6). When plotting the degree of orientation - expressed through *Advani's* orientation tensor [6] - over the length of the flow, a number of characteristic features can be observed (s. Fig. 7):

- Mechanism I: Orientation is increased with flow length.
- Mechanism II: Orientation is increased with time and independent of flow length.
- A maximum orientation is not exceeded, even at very large deformation.
- For the radial, flow mechanism II cannot be observed (\Rightarrow random orientation at $r = 0$).
- Orientation in multi-charge part is significantly weaker.

Figure 7. Orientation in rectangular and circular part

ORIENTATION PREDICTION

The fact that the orientation mechanism is driven by 3-dimensional flow effects (even though fibers are basically in planar orientation) and that both flow and orientation are dominated by the strong anisotropy of the stack of fiber mats, requires a 3-D orientation model to make realistic predictions. The observation that in molded and incinerated parts, the individual mats can still be identified as such, has led to a mesh-type orientation model: Orientation is conceived as the result of a deformation of the fiber mat rather than because of individual fibers rotating. *Dinh* and *Armstrong's* orientation model

$$\psi = \frac{1}{4\pi} \cdot (\mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F} : \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p})^{-3/2} \quad (2)$$

where ψ is the fiber distribution function, \mathbf{F} the inverse of the deformation gradient \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{p} the unit vector that points in the direction of the fiber, describes the orientation behavior of a dilute fiber suspension [5]. The product $\mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F}$ is the Cauchy strain tensor that can be interpreted as an ellipsoid which is a sphere in the undeformed state. The model assumes that the fiber orientation is equivalent to the deformation of the surrounding fluid. Conceiving the fiber mat to be such a deforming fluid (= mesh-type deformation), its orientation can be expressed through Eqn. (2). However, the fiber mesh can only be treated as such as long as the cross-points of two fibers are capable of transferring loads. Since the fiber mesh is connected only through friction, the cross-points will slip at high degrees of orientation, so that further deformation does not lead to a proportional re-orientation (s. Fig. 8). Eqn. (2) was therefore fitted with a phenomenological term to account for imperfect mesh deformation.

The deformation gradient \mathbf{E} is obtained by solving the momentum, continuity and energy equation together with non-isothermal (Arrhenius-type), power-law viscosity model to give a velocity. By integrating the velocity \mathbf{v} over the time, the deformation \mathbf{x} can be obtained. Differentiation with respect to the material coordinate \mathbf{x}_0 gives the deformation gradient \mathbf{E} . In the energy equation only conduction in the z -direction and no convective terms are considered. It is solved using an implicit Finite Difference Method in the thickness direction. The fountain flow region is neglected. Due to the lack of reliable viscosity data for GMT, the velocity (and the orientation) was calculated only for the single-charge moldings.

Figure 8. Sleeve model for imperfect deformation.

Imperfect deformation can be considered by means of a correction term for \mathbf{E} which depends on the crossing angle between two fibers and is weighed by the orientation function. A phenomenological factor C_{II} controls the degree of slip at the cross points of the mesh. The initial orientation of the charge can be accounted for by a "pre-deformed" strain tensor (e.g.: for planar, random orientation (no fibers in the z-direction) the strain ellipsoid takes the shape of a thin, circular disk). At every time step the old deformation state and the extra deformation are superimposed. The computation of the deformation gradient from a given velocity distribution can be performed very efficiently, since the differentiation and integration can be carried out analytically.

The elements of the deformation gradient \mathbf{E} can be interpreted as different deformation modes superimposed in the flow. When plotted over the flow length, the effect of transverse shearing and planar extension becomes obvious (Fig. 9): Near the symmetry axis the material sees some extensional deformation (E_{11}), which is constant over the length of the part. Near the mold wall the material is not deformed at all, due to non-isothermal effects. Between the mold wall and the axis of symmetry the charge is subjected to a strong transverse shear deformation (E_{13}) that increases with flow length. These results are in good agreement with the deformation profile observed in the molding experiments using black tracers.

Figure 9. Extension (E_{11}) and Shear (E_{13}) as a function of flow length and z -coordinate

The resulting orientation distributions in different positions in the thickness direction are averaged over the total thickness and expressed through *Advani's* orientation tensor \mathbf{a} [6]. This integral orientation can be plotted over the flow length and compared to the experimental values. Fig. 10 shows how the orientation in rectangular and circular plates develops with increasing deformation. Qualitatively the results correspond well to the measured orientation distribution. Parameter studies, where viscosity data, the slip factor C_{II} and the initial orientation were varied, showed that the power-law index has only little effect on the final orientation in the part, while the slip factor and the initial orientation have a strong influence on the results. A charge with near planar orientation will hardly be affected by transverse shearing and will re-orient significantly less. This applies for both mold geometries. In the case of radial flow the extension in x - and y -direction is identical which results in no re-orientation of the fibers. In order to produce quantitative results, the initial orientation and the slip factor C_{II} for the material have to be known.

Figure 10. Development of orientation with process time t^* in rectangular and circular plate ($C_{II} = 0$)

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